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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ҚАШШОҚЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШ: ЗАМОНАВИЙ ДУНЁДА АСОСИЙ МУАММОЛАР

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада қашшоқликнинг умумий кўрсаткичлари, Бирлашган Миллатлар Ташкилотининг қашшоқлик бўйича параметрлари ҳамда концепциялар ёритилган. Асосий қисмда Марказий Осиёда қашшоқликнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари ва минтақада ҳар бир давлатда қашшоқлик ҳолати аниқ рақамларда келтирилган. Шунингдек, турли соҳалар кесимида қашшоқликни қисқартириш муаммолари ва мамлакатларнинг иқтисодий заиф жиҳатлари ёритилган. Мақолада Марказий Осиё минтақаси давлатларидан келиб чиқиб қашшоқликни қисқартириш муаммолари таҳлил қилинган. Умумий хулоса қисм сифатида нуфузли халқаро ташкилотлар ва тадқиқотчиларнинг минтақада қашшоқликни қисқартириш юзасидан таклифлари келтириб ўтилган.

Калит сўзлар: Марказий Осиё, қашшоқлик, БМТ, Жаҳон Банки, ижтимоий ҳимоя, Ковид-19, ЯИММ, камбағаллик, иқтисодий ўсиш, минтақа.

Ergashev Umid Arabboy ugli.

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POVERTY REDUCTION IN CENTRAL ASIA: MAIN CHALLENGES IN THE CONTEMPORARY WORLD

ANNOTATION

This article examines the United Nations General Poverty Indicators, aspects and concepts of poverty. In the main part, specific aspects of poverty in Central Asia and the state of poverty in each country of the region are presented in exact figures. Also, in various sectors, the problems of reducing poverty and economic weakness of countries are highlighted. The article analyzes the problems of poverty reduction in Central Asia. In conclusion, the proposals of prestigious international organizations and researchers to reduce poverty in the region are presented.

Key words: Central Asia, penury, UN, World Bank, social protection, Covid-19, GDP, poverty, economic growth, region.

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СОКРАЩЕНИЕ БЕДНОСТИ В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ: ОСНОВНЫЕ ВЫЗОВЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье рассматриваются общие показатели бедности, параметры, аспекты и концепции Организации Объединенных Наций. В основной части в точных цифрах представлены конкретные аспекты бедности в Центральной Азии и состояние бедности в каждой стране региона. Также в различных отраслях выделяются проблемы сокращения бедности и экономической слабости стран. В статье анализируются проблемы сокращения бедности в Центральной Азии. В заключении представлены предложения авторитетных международных организаций и исследователей по снижению бедности в регионе.

Ключевые слова: Центральная Азия, бедность, ООН, Всемирный банк, социальная защита, Covid-19, ВВП, нищета, экономический рост, регион.

Analyzing the problem of poverty, it is worth starting with a description of the main causes of its occurrence as a phenomenon. Most often, poverty as a social disease occurs in societies that are either unable to provide a level of social production sufficient to meet the basic needs of each member, or do not create an effective model for the distribution of the social product.

The UN highlights the following list of parameters that contribute to the spread of poverty in the modern world: low level of education, low quality of the labor force, non-inclusive society, poor quality of medicine and other demographic reasons (overpopulation, forced migration), conflict situations, low competitiveness of products, low efficiency of distribution of public benefits in the economy, inefficient organization of the labor market.

There are also a number of concepts that describe the classes of sources of poverty in society: personal, cultural, structural, geographical causes, dependence on cumulative and cyclical shocks. By combining the ideas of various concepts of poverty, it is possible to identify specific factors in the formation and persistence of poverty in the Central Asian region. On the economic causes of poverty in Central Asia, which can be quantified. These include the level of unemployment in the region, the average level of income among citizens, the low level of economic mobility of the population, institutional factors, including some demographic ones.

Country specifics of poverty in Central Asia.

The countries of the Central Asian region have several systemic problems that seriously affect their poverty. Among them are the unemployment rate; the average level of income of citizens and households; low level of economic mobility; high dependence of the countries of the region on cyclical and cumulative risks; demographic factor. These factors are key to understanding the development of poverty in Central Asia, but they may manifest themselves differently in each country.

1-Infograph. Poverty rate in Central Asia.

Poverty in Kazakhstan.

Kazakhstan has achieved the greatest success in the fight against poverty. According to the World Bank, in 2022, the poverty rate in Kazakhstan was 12.4%. But it should be mentioned that against the backdrop of the COVID-19 pandemic, the poverty rate has risen to 12-14% compared to 2016. The number of people living below the 50th median income is 3.8% of the total population of the country.

“The most significant increase in the number of the poor is expected to come from rural areas, which threatens to increase inequality in Kazakhstan,” said Jean-Francois Marteau, World Bank Country Manager for Kazakhstan. “The country’s average GDP growth has declined after each economic crisis, weighed down by the lackluster productivity growth and over-dependency on hydrocarbons. Therefore, more than ever, Kazakhstan needs to focus on delivering reforms for inclusive economic recovery and higher productivity, as well as ensuring the effectiveness of government programs.”

An important feature of Kazakhstan is its strong socio-economic differentiation; large cities - Astana and Almaty - live better than other regions. The largest number of poor people is concentrated in rural areas - in the Turkestan, Zhambyl and Karaganda regions (except for Karaganda).

Poverty in Kyrgyzstan.

The main causes of poverty in Kyrgyzstan include insufficient development of agriculture; dependence on remittances and the tourism industry. The poverty rate in Kyrgyzstan in 2021 was 33.3% compared to 20% in 2019. About 10% of the country's citizens live at risk of poverty.

The level of extreme poverty in 2021 was 6%, mainly in rural areas. The reasons for the growth in the number of the poor were the COVID-19 pandemic, sanctions against the Russian Federation and a decrease in the flow of remittances from abroad. The factor of spatial disproportions "North-South" is typical for the analysis of the problem of poverty in Kyrgyzstan. The north and the center represented by the capital have the highest rates of development.

Poverty in Uzbekistan.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that 12-15 percent or 4-5 million of the population of our country is in a state of poverty. This means that their daily income does not exceed 10-13 thousand soums. The provision of a poor family with personal computers is 12 times less than that of an average family in the republic, cars - 11 times, air conditioners - 8 times, vacuum cleaners - 4 times, washing machines - 4 times, refrigerators - 2 times, televisions - 1.5 times and mobile phones - 1.5 times.

The poor part of the population not only does not benefit from the rapid economic growth that characterizes the country, but also does not have the opportunity to contribute to the development of society due to limited access to major markets. The state provides free secondary education, guarantees a basic package of medical services that includes primary care, emergency care, care for "socially important and dangerous" conditions and specialized care for populations classified by the government as vulnerable, provides benefits for low-income families.

Poverty in Turkmenistan.

Turkmenistan is characterized by strict filtering of information and the inability to conduct an independent assessment of official data on poverty in the country. According to the authorities of the Republic, 0.4-0.5% of the population were below the poverty line in 2018-2021. According to information from independent sources, the country's population is divided into two groups: those who live on \$1.9/day (40% of the population) and those who live on \$3.1/day (60% of the population).

Poverty in Tajikistan.

Despite significant economic growth, the disappearance of the effect of a low base of economic growth will not allow Tajikistan to quickly reduce poverty. The coronavirus pandemic led to a sharp increase in consumer prices - by 9.2% in 2021. Added to this is the decline in capital inflows in the form of migrant remittances (from 50% to 29% of GDP) due to the tightening of immigration laws and sanctions against Russia. The persistence of the agricultural nature of the economy causes seasonal and "weather" poverty. In this regard, the poverty rate in Tajikistan ranges from 10-13% (independent estimates) to 25.9%.

2-Infograph. Uncertainty around the impact of the war very high, especially among the poor and migrants.

More than ever before, the Central Asian states need sustainable and more resilient growth models. Despite attempts for reforms across the region in the years before the pandemic, several factors which contributed to a loss of momentum loom large such as underdeveloped private sectors, serious defects in the business climate, overreliance on exports of primary commodities, and migrant labor, and weak competition.

Experts at OECD have mentioned three-fold challenges confronting the Central Asian region, which need to be addressed to create the foundations for a sustainable and inclusive economic trajectory.

The first challenge is to ensure that firms and workers emerge strongly from the ongoing crisis. This will require better and targeted support and market discipline.

The second challenge is in the form of structural weaknesses, apparent well before the crisis and have compounded the impact of COVID-19. This requires improving the domestic business climate to create conditions that are more favorable for entrepreneurship, investment, and innovation.

The third challenge is that policymakers must develop policies that could maximize the competitiveness of Central Asia in the future global economy as the world moves towards low-carbon transition and digital transformation. Managing these challenges is essential and critical to ensuring productivity growth, job creation, and investment.

Poverty reduction recommendations should be based on the characteristics of poor households, existing barriers and development priorities, and macroeconomic and micro-level policy options.

In particular, it is proposed:

- development of inclusive business models;
- encouraging structural reforms aimed at affordable employment, progressive taxation, social spending and minimum wage policies;
- development of predominantly labor-intensive sectors and sectors of the economy, both relatively low-productivity industries (agriculture, food and light industry), and high-tech knowledge-intensive industries;
- development of small business in the service sector, in particular, in servicing entrepreneurs in agricultural production, including services for the procurement and storage of products, maintenance of agricultural machinery;
- Creation of a system for the provision of educational and medical services through mobile phones.

The World Bank also looked at how governments can more effectively mobilize tax revenue to protect the poor and finance needed public investment. Suggested measures include:

Firstly, increasing the importance of land and property taxes, which currently constitute a very small part of tax revenues in the countries of Central Asia;

Secondly, increased use of health taxation, such as tobacco, alcohol and sugar-sweetened beverages;

Thirdly, establishing relatively flat rates of income and corporate taxes in the countries of Central Asia so that middle- and low-income people pay a similar share of their income in taxes.

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